

MULTI-SCALE ANALYSIS OF THE AGEING OF A REINFORCED POLYAMIDE 66 IN ETHANOL-BASED FUELS

Camilo A. Cruz¹, Enrico Belmonte^{1,2}, Alexander Lux³, Matthias de Monte¹ and Marino Quaresimin²

¹Corporate Sector Research and Advanced Engineering - Plastics Technology
Robert Bosch GmbH, CR/APP2, Renningen, 70465 Stuttgart, Germany
Email: camilo.cruz@de.bosch.com, web page: <http://www.bosch.com>

²Department of Management and Engineering, University of Padova
Via 8 Febbraio 1848, 2, 35122 Padova PD, Italy
Email: marino.quaresimin@unipd.it, web page: <http://www.unipd.it>

³Diesel Gasoline Systems, Development of Pressure Sensors
Electronics and Advanced Engineering
Robert Bosch GmbH, DGS-ES/EPP1, Postfach 30 02 20, 70442 Stuttgart, Germany
Email: alexander.lux@de.bosch.com, web page: <http://www.bosch.com>

Keywords: Ageing, Fuel, Injection Moulding, Lifetime, Polyamide

ABSTRACT

Accurate lifetime prediction is a cornerstone for the design of more sustainable injection-moulded plastic composite parts. In fact, a more accurate lifetime prediction would reduce the number of prototyping recursions in the development and improve the performance of the parts. Typical factors affecting the lifetime of an injection-moulded part are the process-induced material properties, the mechanical loading scenario and the physicochemical interaction with the environment. This work is focused on this last issue and deals specifically with the environmental ageing of an injection-moulded fibre reinforced polyamide 66 (PA66) composite in contact with liquid ethanol-based fuel. Based on a multi-scale experimental approach, going from the molecular scale (polymer molecular mass) to the macroscopic scale (quasi-static mechanical tensile properties), we identified that physical plasticization by fuel diffusion and random polymer chain scission are relevant degradation mechanisms triggered by the ethanol-based fuel on the injection-moulded fibre reinforced PA66 composite. Polyamide hydrolysis appears as the controlling chemical degradation mechanism. The progressive decrease of the polyamide molecular mass leads to an abrupt embrittlement of the composite when the matrix molecular mass reaches approximately 52 kg/mol (PMMA standard).

1 INTRODUCTION

Composite plastic parts are commonly over-dimensioned given the inaccuracy of the models predicting their lifetime. In fact, lifetime is a crucial factor affecting the design and the dimensioning of a composite plastic part. Furthermore, a more accurate lifetime prediction would correct design failures at earlier development stages and reduce the number of prototyping recursions in the product development. In other words, a more reliable lifetime prediction is a key for improving the performance of a composite plastic part and saving time and money.

Pressure sensors are components currently mounted in diverse fuel-related systems within the car. Those sensors measure fuel pressure – and eventually fuel temperature when integrated with a temperature sensor – in the fuel rail or the inlet pressure to the high pressure pump in direct petrol injection engines. As a component of an engine management system, e.g. the electronic returnless fuel system, the pressure signals measured by those sensors allow the control of the fuel supply to the injectors by modulating the fuel pump power. Nowadays, the housings of the low-pressure sensors (from 6 to 10 bar) are manufactured by injection moulding of glass-reinforced polyamides. During the car operation, those parts are exposed to different environmental agents as, for example, ethanol-based

fuels. A correct dimensioning of such housings is therefore dependent on an accurate lifetime prediction under typical operating conditions.

Lifetime prediction in plastic parts is, nevertheless, a challenging task given the diversity of the physical phenomena – at different spatial and temporal scales – taking place. Typical factors affecting the lifetime of a composite plastic part are, typically, the process-induced material properties, the mechanical loading scenario (type, temperature, frequency, amplitude) and the physicochemical interaction with the environment. As part of a decoupled modelling approach, those different factors are often investigated independently with the aim of reduce the interaction effects and facilitate the analysis. The present work, following this approach, deals fundamentally with the environmental ageing of composite plastic parts. According to Verdu [1], environmental ageing is the slow and irreversible evolution of one or several properties of a given material exposed to environment agents (temperature, liquids and gases). This evolution is the result of modifications of the chemical structures or the material morphologies.

The physicochemical ageing of glass-fibre reinforced polyamide composites in front of automotive fluids has been extensively studied in the literature. The characterisation of the ageing of polyamide composites has been specially focused on the interaction with water and anti-freezing solutions (e.g. water/glycol mixtures). In terms of hydrothermal conditioning, several ageing mechanisms have been identified: physical plasticization through water absorption [2, 3], physicochemical degradation of the matrix/fibre interface [3, 4] and chemical degradation by means of chain scission [2, 3]. According to Thomason and Ali [5], the water uptake in glass-fibre reinforced PA66 composites can be modelled by a Fickian diffusion process with a time dependent diffusion coefficient. In other respects, the reaction mechanisms of the polyamide hydrolysis in pure water have been well established [6, 7] and the influence of diverse acids on the reaction kinetics has been identified. In fact, Merdas et al. [8] determined that acids affect the polyamide 11 hydrolysis basically in two ways: catalysis and amine scavenging. On the other hand, the environmental ageing of polyamide composites in contact with water/glycol mixtures has been also widely studied [9]. Thomason et al. [10] showed, for example, that the weight uptake of PA66 immersed in water/glycol mixtures follows a pseudo-Fickian diffusion process. Plasticization by water/glycol absorption, disentanglement of the polyamide chains by effect of the glycol and statistical chain scission by hydrolysis have been cited as the main ageing mechanisms [9]. In summary, different effects on the composite mechanical performance have been reported as result of the physicochemical ageing of glass-fibre reinforced polyamides in contact with water or water/glycol mixtures as, for example, reduction of the linear viscoelastic storage modulus in the 0-40°C range [10, 11], increase of the impact strength for early ageing times [4, 10, 11] and decrease of the ultimate tensile stress [4, 9].

In comparison with water and anti-freezing mixtures, ethanol-based fuels have been less studied as ageing medium for polyamide composites. The interest for understanding the ageing of polyamide composites in contact with ethanol-based mixtures has grown nevertheless in the last decades due to the introduction of ethanol-based fuels as an alternative automotive combustible. Kallio et al. [12], for example, studied the ageing of polyamide 12 in contact with diverse ethanol-based fuels. They reported loss of plasticiser and reduction of the matrix molecular mass as the main consequences of the ageing process. Using accelerated ageing experiments, Kallio et al. [13] revealed also that the extent of the polyamide 12 degradation increases with temperature and fuel ethanol content.

Apart from the previous studies on polyamide 12, the scientific information concerning the ageing of polyamide composites in front of ethanol-based fuels is poor. The available information is insufficient to establish reliable end-of-life criteria for the injection-moulded polyamide composites parts in contact with ethanol-based fuels. To set the basis for reliable design of polyamide composite parts in contact with ethanol-based fuel mixtures, we studied the physicochemical ageing occurring in a glass-fibre reinforced PA66 injection-moulded part when exposed to ethanol-based fuel mixtures in the 110-130 °C temperature range. This work deals with the physicochemical ageing in absence of external loadings; i.e. we do not consider the so-called mechanical ageing (creep, relaxation, fatigue). This study identifies the main degradation mechanisms triggered by an ethanol-based fuel on an injection-moulded glass-fibre reinforced PA66 composite and discusses the evolution of the composite's quasi-static mechanical properties during the ageing process at the light of structure-properties relationships.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials

One commercial PA66 composite, reinforced with 35 wt% glass fibres, was used in this study. According to the supplier's datasheet, the 35 wt% glass-fibre reinforced PA66 (PA66-GF35) has a density of 1410 kg·m⁻³ (ISO 1183) and a viscosity number (ISO 307, 0.5% in 96% sulphuric acid) of 145 cm³·g⁻¹. Tensile bars (dog bone specimens type 1A) for tensile testing (ISO 527-2) with a nominal thickness of 4 mm were injection-moulded using a single gate located at the extreme of the specimen. Dog bone specimens (type 1A) exhibit a nominal surface-to-volume ratio of 6.6 cm²·cm⁻³ approximately. The forming process was performed in an electric injection moulding machine by setting a mould temperature of 85°C and imposing a barrel temperature profile going from 260 to 285°C (near the nozzle).

2.2 Controlled ageing tests

Tensile bars of PA66-GF35 were aged as moulded, under controlled conditions, by immersion in two different types of ethanol-based fuels. Table 1 presents the composition of the two fuels, E1 and E2, employed in the ageing tests. We used the fuel E2, containing the double of water in comparison to E1, expecting an acceleration of the ageing process. In fact, we supposed that the chemical ageing of the PA66-GF35 in contact with this kind of fuels is mainly driven by hydrolytic processes.

Constituent	Units	Fuel E1	Fuel E2
Ethanol	wt%	93	86
Water	wt%	7	14
Formic acid	ppm	1	0
Acetic acid	ppm	5	0
Hydrochloric acid	ppm	1	0
Sulphuric acid	ppm	4	0

Table 1: Composition of the ethanol-based fuels used in the controlled ageing tests of 4 mm tensile bars injection moulded with PA66-GF35.

Ageing of the PA66-GF35 tensile bars was carried out inside stainless steel autoclaves with nominal capacities of 1 L and 3 L. Autoclaves were filled up to ~80% of their nominal capacity with fuel. Each autoclave was mounted on an electrical heating system coupled with a closed-loop temperature control system, whose measuring point was placed inside the autoclave. PA66-GF35 tensile bars were aged immersed in ethanol-based fuels (E1 and E2) at two constant temperatures: 110 and 130 °C. We used those temperatures because they are close to the current thermal requirements for low-pressure fuel sensors. PA66-GF35 tensile bars were aged in autoclave during different times going from 48 h until 1000 h. Fuel in each autoclave was renewed every week (168 h) in order to reduce the influence of an eventual ageing of the medium. Each fuel renewal required the autoclave to be cooled down close to 70 °C and represented an interruption of the isothermal ageing process during 6 h approximately.

After the isothermal ageing process in autoclave, the PA66-GF35 tensile bars were either kept immersed in fuel at room temperature (~23 °C) or dried back in vacuum at 100 °C during 2 weeks (336 h).

2.3 Characterization methods

Viscosity number was determined according to the norm ISO 327 on samples taken from reference tensile bars (i.e. dry as moulded), aged tensile bars (kept in fuel after ageing) and dry aged tensile bars (dried back after ageing). Samples for viscosity number determination were taken at two different locations in the tensile bar: one at the grip section and other at the reduced section between the

shoulders. Before elution in sulphuric acid, samples were conditioned inside a vacuum oven at 100 °C during 3 h.

Gel Permeation Chromatography (GPC) was carried out in a selected series of samples taken from reference tensile bars (i.e. dry as moulded), aged tensile bars (kept in fuel after ageing) and dry aged tensile bars (dried back after ageing). Objective was to quantify the molecular mass distribution of the polymer matrix in the different composites. A solution of Hexafluoro-2-propanol + 0.05% 3-Fluoroacetic acid-Potassium salt was used as elution medium. Sample solutions ($1.5 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were filtered through a $0.2 \mu\text{m}$ Millipore Millex FG unit and, then, injected in the separation columns at $1 \text{ mL}\cdot\text{min}^{-1}$ and $40 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Molecular weight of the PA66 matrix was determined using a calibration curve obtained with PMMA standards (from $800 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$ to $1820 \text{ g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$).

Tensile tests, according to the norm ISO 527-1A, were performed on reference tensile bars (i.e. dry as moulded), aged tensile bars and dry aged tensile bars in order to characterize the tensile mechanical properties of the different materials. Test speed was set at $5 \text{ mm}\cdot\text{min}$ and strain was measured with a 10 mm extensometer placed in the middle of the bar.

Images of the fracture surfaces in some of the tested tensile bars were obtained with a Field Emission Scanning Electron Microscope (FE-SEM) using an acceleration voltage of 7 kV . Fracture surfaces for FE-SEM analysis were previously prepared with a gold coating.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A graphical correlation between the molecular weight, M_w , of the PA66 matrix measured by GPC and the respective viscosity number for a series of injected samples with different ageing histories is given in the Figure 1.

Figure 1: Molecular mass M_w as function of the viscosity number of the polyamide matrix in injection-moulded PA66-GF35 samples for different ageing histories

In addition to the data of tensile bars dry as moulded and aged in fuel E1, Figure 1 also contains data of tensile bars conditioned under vacuum at different temperatures (previous work). On one hand, tensile bars conditioned under vacuum exhibit an increase of the molecular mass and the polydispersity as result of a poly-condensation process, which is typical of polyamides. On the contrary, tensile bars aged in fuel E1 evidence a reduction of the molecular mass and the

polydispersity, which is characteristic of a statistical chemical degradation process of the polymer chains. In fact, the polydispersity of a linear polymer submitted to random bond-breaking events tends theoretically to 2 [14]. In addition, Chaupart et al. [6] showed that the acidic hydrolysis of polyamides (6, 11 and 12) is consistent with a random chain scission process.

Figure 1 also puts in evidence that the drying (in vacuum oven at 100 °C during 2 weeks) of the tensile bars after aging in fuel E1 has a non-negligible effect on the molecular mass (mean increase of 3.5 kg·mol⁻¹) and viscosity number (mean increase of 12 cm³·g) of the polyamide matrix, as result of a poly-condensation process.

The most practical result from Figure 1 is, however, the proportional relationship between the molecular mass M_w and the viscosity number in the range $M_w < M_{w0}$, being M_{w0} the molecular mass of the PA66 matrix before aging in ethanol-based fuel. The correlation is represented by the continuous regression line ($R^2 = 0.98$) in Figure 1. It means, in practice, that the polyamide molecular mass M_w of any tensile bar aged in ethanol-based fuel could be estimated from the viscosity number, which is a less-costly measurement in comparison with GPC.

Table 2 summarizes the conditions of the different controlled ageing tests and the respective viscosity number results. The increase of 12 cm³·g in the viscosity number caused by the drying process after ageing was also measured for ageing experiments in other fuels (e.g. RSG-E85). We used, therefore, this mean increase to estimate the molecular mass M_w of some tensile bars dried after ageing, in which the viscosity number was not measured.

Ageing fuel	T _{ageing} [°C]	t _{ageing} [h]	Post-drying ⁺	VN [cm ³ ·g]
-	-	-	-	134*
E1	110	1008	No	106
E1	110	3024	No	97
E1	130	48	No	112
E1	130	72	No	110
E1	130	96	No	105
E1	130	168	No	102
E1	130	336	No	98
E1	130	336	Yes	110
E1	130	408	No	95
E1	130	744	No	90
E2	130	168	No	97
E2	130	336	No	91

⁺ Drying in vacuum oven at 100 °C during 2 weeks

* Viscosity number measured on dry as injection-moulded tensile bars

Table 2: Conditions of the controlled ageing tests on 4 mm tensile bars injection-moulded with PA66-GF35 and respective viscosity numbers of the polyamide matrix measured after ageing.

Figure 2 shows typical engineering stress-strain curves measured on reference tensile bars (i.e. dry as moulded), aged tensile bars (in fuel E1) and dry aged tensile bars (dried back after ageing in fuel E1 or E2). A characteristic plasticization or softening effect, evidenced by the reduction of Young's modulus and the enhancement of the strain at break, appears by the diffusion of fuel within the polyamide matrix. In addition to this softening effect, the composite exhibits a progressive degradation process, which is denoted by a gradual reduction of the strain at break. This reduction in the strain at break is related directly with the temperature and the time of the controlled ageing tests. Such behaviour is typical of hydrolytic degradation processes occurring in polyamide matrices, which have been widely documented elsewhere [9, 15]. In Figure 2 we notice furthermore that fuel E2 induces larger composite embrittlement (reduction in the strain at break) than fuel E1 for the same ageing conditions (immersion in fuel at 130 °C during 336, then drying in vacuum at 100 °C during 336 h). This result confirms that the polyamide degradation process is controlled by hydrolysis given the fact that fuel E2 contains the double of water in comparison to E1.

Figure 2: Engineering stress-strain curves of tensile tests performed on PA66-GF35 injection-moulded bars: dry as moulded (black continuous line), aged in fuel (other continuous lines) and dried back aged samples (dashed lines). Ageing conditions are given inside text boxes: fuel; ageing time; ageing temperature

We suppose that no traces of fuel should remain within the polyamide matrix after the drying process (in vacuum oven at 100 °C during 2 weeks) of the aged tensile bars. If it is the case, the softening effect of the fuel on the polyamide should not take place and the matrix should recover its original Young's modulus. Nevertheless, the composite Young's modulus measured on dry aged tensile bars is still lower than the one measured on dry as moulded tensile bars. We believe that this result is explained by a degraded stress-transfer between matrix and glass fibres. We propose two hypothetical phenomena causing this degradation of the matrix-fibre interface: 1) given the different dimensional swelling of the matrix in comparison to the one of the glass fibres (theoretically zero), a tensile loading is localized on the matrix-fibre interface during the swelling of the composite inducing a physical weakening of the interface (or inter-phase), and/or 2) chemical degradation of the sizing by interaction with the ethanol-based fuel.

Looking for an evidence of the previous hypotheses, the fracture surfaces of some of the tested tensile bars, marked in Figure 2 with a black square, were analyzed by means of a FE-SEM. Figure 3 presents then a comparison of the matrix-fibre interface in a dry as moulded specimen with the one found in a specimen aged in E1 at 130 °C during 744 h. The smoother glass surface in the aged specimen suggests a loss of matrix adhesion in comparison with the not aged specimen. This observation is, nevertheless, not conclusive given the fact that in some other regions of the fracture surfaces the differences are less evident. In addition, Fu et al [16] demonstrated that the analysis of post-mortem morphology on fracture surfaces alone is insufficient for concluding on the fibre-matrix interfacial adhesion. A quantitative analysis – either experimental or simulation-based – of the ageing effect on the strength of the matrix-fibre interface is therefore necessary to validate the postulated degradation hypotheses.

Figure 3: FE-SEM images of the matrix-fibre interface taken on the fracture surfaces of two injection-moulded PA66-GF35 tensile bars: dry as moulded (left) and aged in fuel E1 at 130° C during 744 h (right)

All stress-strain curves of the plasticized composites aged in fuel E1, depicted in the Figure 2, overlap the stress-strain curve of the initial plasticized material, i.e. with very low chemical degradation of the matrix. This fact is an additional indicator that the chemical degradation occurring within the polymer matrix exhibits a random character [9, 15]. A useful result of this is that the quasi-static tensile behaviour of any aged composite can be fully characterized by knowing the stress-strain curve of the initial plasticized material and one of the stress-strain coordinates at rupture (σ_r , ϵ_r). Said otherwise, the strain (or stress) at rupture can be used as a global indicator of the composite degradation process.

It is well established in the literature that the entanglements play a fundamental role in the mechanical performance of amorphous (or low semi-crystalline) linear polymers [14, 17]. This fact implies the existence of a critical molar mass, M_c , governing the mechanical performance of the polymer. For polymers with molecular mass larger than M_c , the properties at rupture are practically independent of the molecular mass. On the contrary, polymers with molecular masses around or smaller than M_c exhibit a clear drop in their mechanical properties at rupture.

With the aim to establish a correlation between the mechanical behaviour of the aged composite and the degradation of the polymer matrix, Figure 4 presents the strain at rupture of the composite as a function of the matrix molecular weight (measured by GPC or estimated from the viscosity number) for different ageing conditions. Two series of data are distinguishable in Figure 4: dry condition (i.e. dry as moulded and dry aged specimens) and wet conditions (i.e. aged specimens). The dry series includes also data of tensile bars conditioned under vacuum at different temperatures, which were obtained in a previous work. The data in the dry series show that the quasi-static mechanical behaviour of the PA66-GF35 composite is controlled by the molecular mass of the polyamide matrix. In fact, the PA66-GF35 composite exhibits a weakening (abrupt reduction of the strain at rupture) for PA66 molecular masses lower than a critical molecular mass. In this case, the critical molecular mass M_c of the polyamide matrix in the PA66-GF35 composite is close to 52 kg/mol (PMMA standard).

The critical PA66 molecular mass is not evident from the data in the wet series simply because all experimental data fall in the region $M_w < M_c$. Nevertheless, the data recovered from the wet series show interestingly that the dependence of the strain at rupture on the PA66 molecular weight is practically the same. This result suggests that the wet series can be obtained by scaling up the dry series, where the scaling factor should be directly related to the plasticizing effect caused by the fuel.

Figure 4: Strain at rupture [%] as function of the measured (or estimated) PA66 molecular mass M_w in PA66-GF35 injection-moulded tensile bars for different ageing histories. Error bars represent a 90% confidence interval.

4 CONCLUSION

Environmental ageing of glass-fibre reinforced PA66 in contact with ethanol-based fuels is driven fundamentally by absorption of the water/ethanol mixture and statistical chain scission of the polyamide matrix, where hydrolysis is the controlling chemical degradation mechanism. As consequence of the water/ethanol absorption, a plasticization effect takes place in the composite, which is traduced in a reduction of the Young's modulus and an increase of the ultimate tensile strain. On the other hand, product of the progressive molecular weight reduction an abrupt composite embrittlement occurs around $M_w = 52$ kg/mol (PMMA standard). This critical molecular mass constitutes an engineering criterion for lifetime estimation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the resin supplier for providing the experimental details and results of the GPC measurements presented in this paper. We would like to acknowledge also Mrs. Schestag (Robert Bosch GmbH), Mr. Klostermann (Robert Bosch GmbH) and Ms. Alaswad (German-Jordanian University) for performing the rest of the experimental characterization used in this work.

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